

WAYS OF NEOLOGISM FORMATION IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the formation of neologisms in the modern. New words have been entering English at an ever increasing rate. Although this phenomenon is often associated with new things, processes, and concepts that need names, there is also a great increase, indeed acceleration, in clever, trendy, eye-ear-catching words.

Keywords: *English language, press language, neologisms, word formation.*

INTRODUCTION

The vocabulary of any language is in constant change and dynamics, being its most mobile component. Vocabulary, as the most mobile layer of language, reacts most sensitively to all changes in social, cultural, political, scientific, and other spheres of human life because it is the word that is the "mirror of life".

The creation of new words reflects, first of all, the needs of society in the expression of new concepts that constantly arise as a result of the development of science, technology, culture, social relations, etc. [1].

At the moment, English, as well as many other languages, is experiencing a "neological boom". The huge influx of new words and the need to describe them led to the creation of a special branch of lexicology—neology – the study of neologisms. Neologisms or new words arise in connection with the appearance of new concepts, and objects in different fields of human activity, which need to be given new names.

Neologisms (from the Greek *neos* "new" and *logos* "word") mean words or phrases denoting a new reality (object or concept) that appeared in the language relatively recently and still retain a touch of novelty and strangeness. As recent reproducible lexical units, neologisms are not included in the active vocabulary of the language.

According to statistics, tens of thousands of neologisms appear in developed languages every year, specifically in English, according to R. Burchfield, who developed a four-volume appendix to the Oxford English Dictionary, an average of 800 neologisms appear every year, which indicates the so-called "neological boom".

The main feature of neologism is the absolute novelty of the word for most native speakers. The word is in a state of neologism for a very short time. As soon as it begins to be actively used, it loses the sign of novelty, that is, it gradually enters the lexical system of the language as a commonly used one. Neologisms are associated with all areas of English-speaking society, but a large number of new lexical units appear in connection with the development of computer technology:

multi-user – computer for multiple users;

hardware – computer parts;

software – computer program;

to blitz out – destroy part of the data in the computer's memory.

Most of the neologisms associated with the use of computers in everyday life are formed using the abbreviated form *tele*. For example:

telepost – a place in the house where a computer is located;

teleshopping, *telebanking* – financial or trading operations using a computer.

A relatively new semantic group is considered to be neologisms on space topics:

space-bike, *mini-bike* – auto lets;

cargo module – cargo compartment of a spacecraft;

UFO – unknown flying objects, etc.

In the field of fine art, there is a rapid process of experimentation, and new writing styles and stylistic techniques are being created:

minimalism – a design or style in which the simplest and fewest elements are used to create the maximum effect. (thematic "fine-grained");

ABC art – art that simplifies and decomposes color and shape into elementary parts;

Op art – art using optical effects;

revivalism – a school of modern painting returning to traditional forms and techniques;

action painting – painting by spraying, etc.

In the field of cinema, television, and video technology, many new technical means have appeared:

inflight movies – movies on board an airplane;

chat show – interviews with a celebrity on TV;

kidvid – TV shows for kids.

A large number of neologisms appear in connection with social movements.

For example, the English language owes many new words to feminism: *libbie* is a suffragette, a feminist [2]. It is thanks to women's movements that some English words ending in *-man* have changed, acquiring a more gender-neutral form:

policeman – police officer, chairman – chairperson.

According to their structure and method of formation, neologisms in the language of the newspaper are represented by several variants. The most characteristic ways of forming neologisms in the language of an English newspaper are word formation (word composition, affixation, conversion, abbreviations) and borrowings from other languages [3].

A word composition is a fusion of two or more bases to form a new word. For English compound words, the most frequent formations are those consisting of two bases:

read-in – readers competition;

recite-in – reciter contest;

swim-in – swimming competition;

lobby-in – conference on political issues;

break-in – intrusion into the privacy of citizens (violation of the secrecy of correspondence, eavesdropping on telephone conversations);

push-over – an easily insurmountable obstacle;

drop-out – a young man who dropped out of school;

build-up – accumulation of military forces;

high-rise – multi-story building;

cloth-cap – worker;

be-in – friendly meeting;

a write-off – out of use.

Another way of forming neologisms is affixation – the formation of new words using suffixes and prefixes. The newspaper style is characterized by the appearance of affixed neologisms with a certain set of affixes, as well as an unusual combination of bases and affixes [4]. Affixes that are unproductive in other speech styles often find new use. In many cases, such affixes develop new meanings that were previously unusual for them, for example, the suffix *-ship*.

This Anglo-Saxon suffix was once used to form abstract nouns with the meaning of a state, or a position, for example: friendship, leadership, or lordship [5]. In newspaper vocabulary, the suffix *-ship* in combination with the morpheme *-man* forms abstract nouns with the meaning of quality, attribute:

brinkmanship – balancing on the brink of war;

craftsmanship – the art of influencing the masses;

showmanship – the ability to show the product's face, to throw dust in the eyes;

statesmanship – the wisdom of a statesman.

The same should be said about the *unproductive* suffix *dom*, which in the newspaper vocabulary began to be used to form new words and thus gained

productivity, for example:

bogdom – a dead end in life;

officialdom – official circles;

suckerdom – a parasite.

In newspaper English, one can find neologisms formed as a result of combining the suffix -er with the basics of noun and verb names. For example:

school leaver – graduate of the school;

primary schooler – primary school student;

senior (junior) graders – students of senior (junior) classes;

marcher - a demonstrator.

The formation of new words using prefixes and their frequent use is also characteristic of the press language. Recently, many words with the prefix -non have appeared in newspapers:

non-access to nuclear weapons – non-admission to nuclear weapons;

non-affiliated union - an American trade union that is not part of a larger union of trade unions;

non-belligerent country – a country that did not participate in the war;

non-content – voting against the proposal (in the House of Lords);

non-union, non-unionist – not a member of a trade union.

Many new words arise as a result of conversion, i.e. the transition of a word from one part of speech to another, leading to the formation of a new word without changing its initial form. Neologisms formed through conversion are widespread in newspaper vocabulary, their presence is one of the distinctive features of the newspaper style itself. Most often these are verbs formed from nouns and nouns formed from verbs. It should be noted that in the newly formed word, meanings often develop that are only indirectly related to the base word. For example, in the *to hit* – *a hit* pair, you can observe an interesting development of the meaning of the noun. As a result of a number of transfers and reinterpretations of the meaning of a hit, it has come to mean success or what has success.

A similar development can be observed in the following pairs:

to print – *a print*; the noun *print* has developed the meaning of circulation, i.e. the entire number of printed copies;

to cut – *a cut*; the noun has acquired the meanings of reduction and cancellation.

In newspaper vocabulary, especially in the part of it that relates to political events, and advertising, partially substantive words are often found, a kind of conversion in which a word acquires only some signs of a noun, for example, an article or a plural form. For example:

the unemployed – a man with no employment;
casuals – comfortable shoes for every day;
home beautifuls – household items (bathrobe, flip-flops, etc.);
the coloureds - colored population;
locals – local trade unions and their representatives.

The reverse derivation is the process of forming heads by truncating the suffix from correlative nouns such as televise "to show on television" from "television".

Another type of formation of new words is an abbreviation. The abundance of abbreviated words, especially in the headlines, is a characteristic feature of the newspaper's language. Some abbreviations found in English newspapers appeared in the newspaper and later became common for all styles of speech; others were rarely found outside the newspaper; others came to the newspaper from the language of technical literature, business language, i.e. from other functional styles.

There are four types of abbreviations: abbreviations, acronyms, truncations, merges. The peculiarity of truncations is their reduced stylistic coloring, and, accordingly, their use is limited to the framework of colloquial speech. Truncation is typical for various types of slang (school, newspaper, sports):

sis – sister;
doc – doctor;
telly – television – TV;
zine – magazine;
specs – spectacles – glasses;
flu – influenza;
mizzy – miserable – pathetic.

Abbreviations and acronyms occupy a large place among abbreviations.

Technical terms, names of groups and organizations are most often abbreviated.

Abbreviations are usually used more often than the terms themselves:

VCR – video-cassette recorder;
PC – personal computer;
BUT – home Office;
E.V.A. (extravehicular activity) – work in outer space;
R.E.M. - rapid eye movement

Unlike abbreviations, acronyms are pronounced as full words:

SALT – Strategic Arms Limitation Talks;
UNESCO – United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization;
WHO – World Health Organization;
WAY - World Assembly of Youth - an international youth assembly.

The English language is characterized by such a way of forming new words as merging – composing one word from two truncated ones. Thus, phonemes overlap at the junction of two words:

faction – fact + fiction is fiction based on documentary facts.

Amerasian – American + Asian – a person of American-Asian descent.

docudrama – documentary drama – documentary drama.

fruiice – fruit + juice – fruit juice.

slimnastics – slim + gymnastics – gymnastics for weight loss.

wordrobe – word + wardrobe – vocabulary

The bulk of bullion words are used in the media and in advertising. Due to the novelty and surprise of the form, they attract attention and have a certain pragmatic effect on the reader. Words-ingots or word-constrictions play an important role in modern colloquial and newspaper-journalistic speech, that is, in those styles of speech communication where the desire for efficiency of presentation is especially noticeable.

Another common way of the appearance of neologisms in the newspapers is borrowing from another language. Many people associate the activation of the process of borrowing vocabulary with social reasons, including political ones, which cannot but find its reflection, first of all, in the language of the media and the press. The language integrates foreign vocabulary, thereby expanding the vocabulary as a result of strengthening international contacts. Such words are gradually assimilated by the language due to multiple repetitions. Thus, the French *detente* (easing of international tension), which is now often used in the English and American press, appeared as a consequence of the peace-loving policy of the Soviet Union, which proclaimed the easing of international tension by preserving world peace.

Among the borrowings used in the language of the newspaper, you can find a lot of cripples, i.e. literal translations from a foreign language. For example:

spaceship – a spaceship vehicle;

to monitor sputniks – monitor satellites by radio;

to walk in the open space – to go into outer space;

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